

RESEARCH ON GEOLOGICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL CAUSES OF DILUTION IN COMPLEX-STRUCTURED GOLD ORE DEPOSITS

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Abstract. Ensuring the level of rational use of subsoil in the extraction of ore deposits with a complex structure is considered one of the urgent issues and requires a constant analysis of the factors affecting the effectiveness of the activities of the mining enterprise. The article examines the geological and technological reasons that lead to ore dilution.

Keywords: ore, useful component, loss, dilution, extraction, evaluation, quality management.

The features of uneven distribution of mineral and element concentrations in various mineral deposits have been identified, one of the important consequences of this natural phenomenon in relation to the issue under consideration is the formation laws of the structure of conductive fragments, their proportion and parts of the ore body.

According to the results of numerous tests and generalized data, the general laws of the formation of conductive fields for various deposits have been determined. For almost all types of deposits, according to its structural nature, the conductive plots make up 20-40 % of the volume of the ore body, 70-90% of the reserves of the useful component. For mercury, gold and other deposits, the ratio of the volume of ore body condensing parts to its total volume is 10-25%, in most cases for other ore and scattering deposits - less than 50%.

The inhomogeneity of the areas of concentration of useful components greatly affects the accuracy of the search and evaluation of mining reserves. This is one of the important reasons for the discrepancy between the actual and project indicators of the quantity and quality of reserves, as well as the technical and economic indicators of mining. At the same time, the methods of reliable identification and assessment of the concentration zones of the useful component have not been improved by modern testing methods. If the primary geological sample is not reliable enough, it is impossible to determine the true morphology of the mineralized field, even with any details of the search grid.

The smallest amount of the mineral in certain samples that distinguish the industrial part of a mineral from the non-industrial part of industrial importance and are used in determining its limits is called "grade". The amount of grade is determined in the composition of the conduits only when there is no clear geological boundary between the minerals and the waste rocks, and its condition is determined by the results

of sampling in an industrially suitable part of the mine[1]. As a parameter determining the limit of the industrial part of the mineral, the size of the on-grade amount is determined by direct calculation or methods of options.

Ore dilution is not only affected by geotechnology, but also by the presence of nonconductive ore and waste rocks in the limited balance reserve, and is divided into mining-technological and geological-economic types of dilution [2-4].

Mining-technological dilution is caused by the mixing of waste rocks into ore in different quantities and places[5].

Geological-economic dilution occurs in the natural process of mining formation in accordance with the requirements of modern exploration and, on the other hand, the technology of limiting the uneven distribution of a useful component.

The value of the maximum dimensions of the plots of waste rocks, which can be included in the mining contour, is determined primarily for technical reasons, depending on the methods of opening a projected mine and mining method, taking into account the possibility of selective mining of minerals or sorting it in a face[6].

At the initial stage of geological and economic assessment, due to the natural unevenness of the mineralized area and the imperfection of the technology for delimiting the contour of reserves, ore reserves are reduced in quality[7]. Therefore, when dividing the contour of the mine, there is a need to independently assess the volume of the condensation of the waste rocks, which are not taken into account in the balance reserve, and the share of nonconditioned ore.

For different mineral deposits, the proportion of nonconditioned fragments varies with the total ore mass volume, with a quantitative predominance in the medium. The proportion of nonconditioned fragments relative to the mass of ore for the gold ore deposit is 40-90%, for polymetallic ore deposits 30-70%, for rare metal deposits 35-80%, for tin deposits 75-95%.

The value of the geological-economic degeneration coefficient is mainly 0,8 (80%) and more for most deposits in accordance with the natural properties of minerals, the technology of design sampling and delimiting the contour of reserves, as well as the geology of ore extraction and enrichment, as well as the conditions.

The study and management of factors affecting the quality of minerals creates the possibility of rational use of the Earth's crust, excessive spending as a result of loss and dilution, as well as reducing the negative impact on the environment, increasing the socio-economic potential of the enterprise.

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